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AN INVESTIGATION ON THE INFLUENCE OF EMOTIONAL APPEALS ON PURCHASE INTENTIONS IN OUTSTANDING PRINT ADVERTISEMENTS.

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ABSTRACT

In terms of emotional appeals, both positive and negative emotional appeals in award-winning advertisements can trigger the intention to make a purchase. The advertisement recall for negative emotional appeals in both award-winning advertisements and in regular advertisements was found to be stronger than that for positive emotional appeals. As a result, this study suggested that outstanding advertisements with negative emotional appeals could successfully attract the curiosity and attention of consumers. Used creatively, the impressions caused by negative emotions could be reduced to increase consumers' purchase intentions and advertisement recall. This study also analyzed the design forms and contents of both award-winning advertisements and regular advertisements. It is hoped that the results can be used as a reference for the design of print advertisements.

Keywords: emotional appeals, print advertisements, purchase intentions.

INTRODUCTION

In a competitive advertising market, the issue of how to increase the effectiveness of advertisements has always been a popular research issue. Scholars have investigated this issue from various aspects. One of these aspects is creativity. It has only been in the last two decades that the effectiveness of creative advertisements has been discussed. Before this time, discussion on creative thinking was usually from artistic perspective, and the commercial effect was not taken into consideration. Since then, outstanding advertisements have been broadly investigated and

discussed. However, it is time consuming and expensive to produce a outstanding advertisement, which arouses the doubts of the advertisers, as advertising strategies need to be instantaneous and effective. Therefore, under such consideration, advertisers may give up the idea of producing outstanding advertisements. Moreover, some researchers have indicated that although outstanding advertisement can win awards, they may not necessarily contribute any commercial effect. For example, Till, and Baack, (2005) found that although outstanding advertisements may trigger independent advertisement recall, they fail to contribute to other elements. Therefore, some advertisers will doubt whether the effectiveness of outstanding advertisements is indeed much higher than that of regular advertisements. However, most studies support the idea that outstanding advertisements are effective and are an indispensable element. For example, Kover, Goldenberg, and James, (1995) found that most consumers' attitudes towards outstanding advertisements are positive, and that outstanding advertisements not only increase consumers' brand loyalty and memory but also helps products become more persuasive (Yang, and Smith, 2009). Furthermore, Pick, and Clay, (1991) and Ang, and Low, (2000), in an analysis on consumers' viewing of outstanding advertisements, indicated that outstanding advertisements can trigger emotions and further increase consumers' recall and preference for the brand. Outstanding advertisements can affect consumers' decision-making (Smith, Chen, and Yang, 2008) and can increase consumers' advertising attitude and purchase intentions, and can affect their emotional response (Kover, et al., 1995). Advertising creativity

can also increase the rating of products (Peracchio, and Meyers-Levy, 1994). In a recent study, Sasser, and Kosl, (2008) summarized the research findings concerning outstanding advertising in recent years based on a literature review from three aspects: an individual aspect, an environmental aspect and a thought process aspect. As a result, outstanding advertisements are commercially effective and can trigger a stronger emotional response from consumers. This study investigated both outstanding advertisements and regular advertisements in order to understand the differences in consumers' responses to them and their advertising effects.

It was found in the literature review that emotions such as pleasure and non-pleasure, aggressiveness and non-aggressiveness, etc. have been used as variables in various studies on advertisements. Schmitt, and Blass, (2008) used the emotion of fear as a variable to investigate whether advertisements can attract consumers' attention and change their behavior and attitude. In addition, LaTour, and Zahra, (1989) suggested that when viewers have a positive attitude while watching advertisements targeting fear, such advertisements make them feel energetic instead of feeling nervous. Kotler, and Armstrong, (1994) indicated that the use of emotional appeals is an attempt to control any party of positive or negative emotions, which can stimulate consumers' purchase intentions. Using the study on advertisements that target fear as an example, it seems that the advertising response to fear appeal is high. Thorson and Friestad (1989) conducted an experimental study and indicated that both the response rate and memory of advertisements targeting fear are higher than those of warm, joyful or non-emotional advertisements (Mehta, and Purvis, 2006). As long as customers are positive, such advertisements can increase their preference for the brand, as well as their interest in purchasing it (Aaker, and Stayman, 1990; Burke, and Edell, 1989; Pieters, and Klerk-Warmerdam, 1996). However, it is generally accepted that positive emotions can better urge consumers to make a purchase, and such a phenomenon is particularly obvious in the advertisements of unsubstantial products and services (e.g. travel services, express delivery services, banks, cram schools, etc.) However, based

on practical observation, this study found that negative emotional appeals are more frequently used in award-winning advertisements than in regular advertisements. The finding raised a further question: Is consumer purchase intention affected by creativity or emotional appeals? Therefore, this study used creativity and emotional appeals as variables to understand the differences in the use of emotional appeals between outstanding advertisements and regular advertisements, and to investigate the influence of emotional appeals on purchase intention. This study analyzed the design forms and contents of both outstanding advertisements and regular advertisements in order to understand whether there is a difference, based on the content analysis method used in the study on advertisements conducted by Naccarato, and Neuendorf, (1998).

Hypothesis A: Consumers' purchase intentions for outstanding (award-winning) advertisements are higher than that for regular (non-award winning) advertisements.

Hypothesis B: The advertisement recall for positive advertisements is stronger than that for negative advertisements.

Hypothesis C: There is a difference in the design forms and content between outstanding (award-winning) advertisements and regular (non-award winning) advertisements.

This study included three stages: Study 1 was the investigation on the purchase intentions for both outstanding advertisements and regular advertisements; Study 2 was the investigation on the advertisement recall for both positive advertisements and negative advertisements; and Study 3 was the investigation of the design forms and contents of both outstanding advertisements and regular advertisements, using the content analysis method.

METHOD

STUDY 1: THE INVESTIGATION ON PURCHASE INTENTIONS FOR OUTSTANDING ADVERTISEMENTS AND REGULAR ADVERTISEMENTS .

To investigate whether outstanding advertisements can better attract consumers' purchase intentions than regular advertisements during the purchase of products and to understand whether the emotional

appeals used in advertisements can also affect consumers' purchase intentions.

Subjects and procedures

Sixteen graduate school students aged 24-30 who had purchased unsubstantial products were requested to classify 124 advertisement samples (62 award-winning advertisements and 62 non-award winning advertisements). The samples were mixed together and the subjects had to classify them without the knowledge of which advertisements were award-winning ones. Study 1 included two periods of classification. In the first classification, the subjects were requested to classify 124 samples into two groups: purchase and non-purchase. After taking a break, in the second classification, the subjects were requested to classify the purchase and non-purchase groups into positive emotions and negative emotions, without a time limit.

Samples

The samples of award-winning service advertisements were randomly collected from the "TAPA Awards 30 Years Best Collections" and "4th and 5th Times Advertising Awards," excluding TV advertisements and outdoor advertising. A total of 62 samples were randomly selected. The TAPA Awards is the advertising design competition held by the China Times in Taiwan. This was the first advertising theme competition to be held in Taiwan and has been held continuously since 1979. Starting in 1989, competitors from other Chinese regions were invited to participate in the competition. It is now an annual Chinese advertising design competition held for the Chinese regions.

The samples of regular service advertisements were collected from the bestseller magazines listed in the "2008 and 2009 Publication Annuals" prepared by the Government Information Office, Executive Yuan. The bestseller magazines were selected from various categories, including: news, finance and economics, popular fashion, art history, language learning, life science and technology, entertainment, cuisine and computer software. There were 7 or 8 samples randomly selected from the bestseller magazines of each category listed in 2008-2009 Publication Annuals, with a total of 62 samples selected.

Results

The results in Table 1 indicated that award-winning service advertisements could better attract subjects

to purchase products, and that the purchase intentions were approximately 37% higher than for non-award winning ones. Advertisements with positive emotions could better attract consumers to purchase products, and the purchase intentions were approximately 5% higher than for those with negative emotions. The purchase intentions for award-winning advertisements with positive emotions were approximately 20% higher than for non-award winning ones. The purchase intentions for award-winning advertisements with negative emotions were 17% higher than for non-award winning ones. The purchase intentions for award-winning advertisements with negative emotions were also 16% higher than for non-award winning advertisements with positive emotions.

Regular advertisements (62 sample)				Award-winning advertisements (62 sample)			
Purchase	Positive (4 sample)	3%	5%	Purchase	Positive (29 sample)	23%	42%
	Negative (25 sample)	2%			Negative (24 sample)	19%	
Non-purchase	Positive (44 sample)	35%	45%	Non-purchase	Positive (3 sample)	2%	7%
	Negative (12 sample)	10%			Negative (6 sample)	5%	

Table 1 Purchase intentions ratios

Study 2: The investigation on the advertisement recall for positive advertisements and negative advertisements.

To use the advertisements of unsubstantial products as examples to investigate whether different emotional appeals will affect consumers' advertisement recall.

Subjects and procedures

Sixteen subjects participating in Study 1 received two electronic questionnaires on the day after the experiment without prior notice. Each questionnaire included the images of 32 samples of service advertisements. The subjects were requested to recall the advertisements they had seen yesterday, write down the numbers and then return the questionnaires. The questionnaires had to be completed on the day of distribution, and only information from the questionnaires returned on that day was included in the recall data. A total of eight questionnaires were returned within the time limit.

Samples

The investigation of the subjects' recall data was designed according to the results of their

classification obtained in Study 1. The first electronic questionnaire included the advertisements that could trigger the subjects' purchase intentions. According to the results of Study 1, eight samples of advertisements with positive appeals that could trigger the subjects' purchase intentions and eight samples with negative appeals that could trigger the subjects' purchase intentions were selected. In addition, an additional 16 samples that were not shown in Study 1 were included, for a total of 32 advertisement samples. The second electronic questionnaire included the advertisements that failed to trigger the subjects' purchase intentions. According to the results of Study 1, eight samples of advertisements with positive appeals that failed to trigger the subjects' purchase intentions and eight samples with negative appeals that failed to trigger the subjects' purchase intentions were selected. An additional 16 samples that were not shown in Study 1 were included, for a total of 32 advertisement samples.

Results

The results in Table 2 indicated that the subjects' recall for the advertisements triggering their purchase intentions were 4% higher than for those failing to trigger their purchase intentions. The recall for advertisements with negative emotions that triggered purchase intentions was 9% higher than for those with positive emotions. The recall for advertisements with negative emotions that failed to trigger purchase intentions was 22% higher than for those with positive emotions.

Subjects	Gender	Accuracy rate of purchase intention	Accuracy rate of emotional appeals		Accuracy rate of non-purchase intention	Accuracy rate of emotional appeals	
			P	N		P	N
A	F	94%	P	75%	91%	P	75%
			N	100%		N	88%
B	F	78%	P	38%	72%	P	25%
			N	63%		N	88%
C	M	88%	P	75%	72%	P	25%
			N	75%		N	63%
D	M	97%	P	100%	94%	P	100%
			N	100%		N	75%
E	M	81%	P	63%	84%	P	63%
			N	63%		N	75%
F	M	100%	P	100%	88%	P	75%
			N	100%		N	75%
G	F	75%	P	38%	63%	P	21%
			N	63%		N	100%
H	M	75%	P	100%	88%	P	100%
			N	100%		N	100%
Total		86%	P	74%	82%	P	61%
			N	83%		N	83%

Table 2 The results of the advertisement recall of eight subjects

Study 3: The investigation of the design form and content of advertisements using the content analysis method.

The content analysis method was used to analyze the differences in design form between outstanding advertisements and regular advertisements.

Subjects and procedures

The advertising design elements were collected from relevant literature, and three design teachers were requested to write down the forms and contents required in the advertisements of unsubstantial products. In addition, this study applied the analysis method used by Naccarato and Neuendorf (1998). A total of 105 design forms and 15 design contents were analyzed. Two experts were requested to analyze the design elements of the 124 advertisement samples in Study 1. One expert was a lecturer in a department of design, while the other was a designer with more than 10 years of working experience. The two experts viewed hardcopies of the advertisements (A4 size) together to analyze the design forms and contents. When there was a difference in the analysis result, they discussed with each other to make their final assessment.

Samples

The samples were the same as those used in Study 1.

Results

The results shown that in terms of composition form, a horizontal line composition was mainly used in both outstanding advertisements and in regular advertisements. A horizontal layout was applied to most of the award-winning advertisements, while a vertical layout was applied to most of the regular advertisements. Most of the outstanding advertisements and regular advertisements were in a block letter format. The titles of award-winning advertisements were mainly in the lower left corner, while those of regular advertisements were mainly in the upper half of the layout. The font size of award-winning advertisements was mainly smaller than 30pt, while that of regular advertisements were mainly approximately 70pt. The number of characters in the titles of both outstanding advertisements and regular advertisements was less than ten. The proportion of the major visual area of both outstanding advertisements and regular advertisements was less than 10%. The location of the major visual area of award-winning advertisements was mainly in the middle, while that of regular advertisements was in the upper half of the layout. The major technique used in both outstanding advertisements and regular advertisements was photography. The overall proportion of photographs used in award-winning advertisements was 100%, while that used in regular advertisements was 70% and 80%. The overall proportion of the characters in outstanding advertisements was 10%, while that in regular advertisements was 20%. The overall proportion of illustrations used in award-winning advertisements was 60% and 90%, while that in regular advertisements was 10%. Tables were not used in award-winning advertisements, while the overall proportion of tables used in regular advertisements was between 10 and 30%. The results shown in Appendix 4 indicated that in terms of the design contents, the most frequently used one in outstanding advertisements was corporate image, followed by image symbol. The most frequently used one in regular advertisements was explanatory appeal followed by attractive price.

The most frequently used design content in advertisements with positive appeals and those with negative appeals was corporate image. The most frequently used design content in the advertisements with non-purchase and positive appeals was an

attractive price, while that used in those with non-purchase and negative appeals was corporate image.

DISCUSSION

According to the results obtained from the Study 1, there is a difference in the use of emotional appeals between award-winning advertisements and regular advertisements. Positive appeals are used more frequently in regular advertisements to attract consumers, while negative appeals are used less frequently. It was inferred from the results of purchase intentions obtained in Study 1 that when choosing unsubstantial products, the subjects would not completely reject the products with negative appeals. On the contrary, it was found in the comparison between award-winning advertisements and regular advertisements that the purchase intentions for award-winning advertisements with negative appeals were 15% higher than for those with positive appeals. It is clear that the use of advertisements with negative appeals in unsubstantial products, such as weight loss advertisements or bank insurance, can trigger purchase intentions. All types of negative appeals can trigger the consumers' purchase intentions.

The comparison of the effect between award-winning and non-award winning advertisements also revealed that the effect of award-winning advertisements on purchases is significantly stronger than that of regular advertisements. The purchase intentions for award-winning advertisements were 37% higher than for regular advertisements. In addition, the subjects' purchase intentions for award-winning advertisements with negative appeals were also 17% higher than for regular advertisements. This data indicated that outstanding advertisements with negative appeals are highly accepted by consumers and the consumers' purchase intentions are high as well, which is unlike the regular advertisements with negative appeals that reduce consumers' purchase intentions. Yang, and Smith, (2009) also indicated that both the effectiveness of the persuasiveness and emotional effects (positive effect) are good. In regard to the use of negative appeals, Kotler, and Armstrong, (1996) indicated that the use of emotional appeals is an attempt to control any party of positive or negative emotions, which can stimulate the consumers' purchase

intentions. It can be inferred that the use of emotional appeals in outstanding advertisements not only has a good effect (Albers-Miller, and Stafford, 1999) but also increases the persuasiveness of the advertisements. Negative emotions in outstanding advertisements can trigger purchase intentions, while those in regular advertisements cannot trigger them. The reason may be that human beings are more curious about new things and will slightly reduce the negative emotions due to curiosity, which triggers their intention to investigate and thus stimulates their purchase intentions. Moreover, the negative appeals in outstanding advertisements are usually expressed in a humorous way, which makes viewers laugh. Therefore, such appeals are not entirely negative and can increase purchase intentions.

The investigation on advertisement recall indicated that the subjects' recall for the advertisements of unsubstantial products they intend to purchase is stronger than for those of the products they do not intend to purchase, which is consistent with the results of past studies. Consumers' recall for the products they are interested in or have a favorable impression on (Biener, Wakefield, Shiner, and Siegel, 2008) is stronger and is easier to store in short-term memory. In terms of the recall for emotional appeals, the recall for negative emotions was 20% stronger than that for positive emotions. Schmitt, and Blass, (2008) indicated in the study on stop smoking advertisements that scary advertisements or images can increase people's memory and enable the subjects to be willing to change their attitude towards smoking. However, excessively chilling or disgusting images will trigger people's protection mechanisms to forget or refuse what they have seen. In the experiments on eight subjects' advertisement recall, it was found that the subjects' recall for outstanding advertisements with negative appeals was stronger than for other advertisements, while their recall for regular advertisements with positive appeals was the weakest. This result was consistent with that obtained from the study conducted by Mehta, and Purvis, (2006), suggesting that it is easy for advertisements with strong emotions to trigger consumers' recall. In outstanding advertisements, the flexible use of strong emotional and negative appeals can increase consumers' purchase intentions,

as well as their recall. In regular advertisements, positive emotions are frequently used to guide consumers to purchase products. However, the results indicated that the effectiveness of positive emotions is not significant, which fails to trigger the consumers' recall and purchase intentions. It was found that the forms and expressions of regular advertisements are quite similar to one another and there is no significant uniqueness in them. Therefore, it is hard to make regular advertisements appealing to consumers. As the amount of information received by current consumers has increased by more than 100-fold of that in the past, it is hard for print advertisements without unique characteristics or content to attract consumers. In addition, it seems that consumers do not have any strong preference for the emotional expression pattern in the advertisements. As long as there is creativity in the advertisements, the consumers' purchase intentions can be triggered. Therefore, one of the approaches to increase the effectiveness of advertisements in the future is to produce outstanding advertisements with novelty and uniqueness.

It is generally accepted that there are no rules in outstanding advertising, especially when it is a unique conversation mode of individual thinking. In addition, it seems that its ingenuity and playfulness are uncatchable. However, the forms and contents of outstanding advertisements can be regularized and standardized in research, in order to probe into relevant aspects. Similar to the study of Goldenberg, Mazursky, and Solomon, (1999), where creative thinking was organized, this study used content analysis to analyze outstanding advertisements and regular advertisements. It was found that there is a difference in the design forms and contents between outstanding advertisements and regular advertisements. The proportions of images and characters in outstanding advertisements are 90% and 10%, respectively. Photographs are the major technique used to convey information, and illustrations are also used sometimes in the design. In regard to the overall design, photographs and characters are frequently used. The major design content is corporate image. The proportions of images and characters in regular advertisements are 70% and 30%, respectively. Information is mainly conveyed by the combination of photographs and

characters, and tables are sometimes attached to give explanations. The elements in the overall design are more complicated. As for the design content, explanatory appeals and an attractive price are mainly used. According to the results summarized above, outstanding advertisements should be used as the standard to amend the design of regular advertisements. The amendments include: 1) The proportions of images and characters in the design should be 90% and 10%, respectively. Images should be used mainly in the design and the titles should be interesting and related to the images. The number of characters should be limited to avoid visual confusion. 2) Avoid using too many elements in the layout. Images, characters, and tables should not be shown together in the screen to avoid obscuring the appeal of the advertisements. 3) The location in the screen should be flexibly used to avoid centering the major visual area in the upper half of the layout.

Corporate image is frequently used as the design content in award-winning advertisements. It can be inferred that corporations attach more importance to their own image and are willing to adopt more time consuming and expensive advertisements, as well as novel ideas. Therefore, they are also willing to adopt negative appeals to express corporate image. For example, advertisements where bankers steal customers' money can be seen in bank advertisements. On the contrary, the most frequently used design contents in regular advertisements are explanatory appeals and attractive prices. Compared with the former ones, this type of advertisement mainly focuses on pleasant and complicated information. It seems that such advertisements are more rational, because they will attract consumers with price discounts first, followed by the use of characters and tables to explain the advantages of the products. However, the results obtained in this study indicated that such advertisements fail to trigger consumers' purchase intentions and recall. Therefore, it is advised to adopt the design forms of outstanding advertisements in future advertisement designs.

REFERENCES

- Aaker, D. and Stayman, D. (1990) Measuring audience perceptions of commercials and relating them to ad impact. *Journal of Advertising Research*, Vol.30, No.4, 7-17.
- Albers-Miller, Nancy D. (1996) Designing cross-cultural advertising research: a closer look at paired comparisons. *International Marketing Review*, Vol.13, No.5, 59 -75.
- Albers-Miller, Nancy D. and Stafford, Marla Roayne. (1999) An international analysis of emotional and rational appeals in services vs goods advertising. *The Journal of Consumer Marketing*, Vol.16, No.1, 42-57.
- Ang, S.H. and Low, S.Y.M. (2000) Exploring the dimensions of ad creativity", *Psychology and Marketing*, Vol.17, No.10, 835-854.
- Baack, Daniel W., Wilson, Rick T. and Till, Brian D. (2008) Creativity and memory effects. *Journal of Advertising*, Vol.37, No.4, 85-94.
- Biener, L., Wakefield, M., Shiner, C.M., Siegel, M. (2008), "How Broadcast Volume and Emotional Content Affect Youth Recall of Anti-Tobacco Advertising. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, Vol.35, No.1,14-19.
- Burke, M. and Edell, J. (1989) The impact of feelings on ad-based affect and cognition. *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol.26, No.1, 69-83.
- Frazer, C.F., Sheehan, K.B., Patti, C.H. (2002), "Advertising strategy and effective advertising: Comparing the USA and Australia. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, Vol.8, No.3, 149-164.
- Goldenberg, J., Mazursky, D., Solomon, S. (1999) The fundamental templates of quality ads. *Marketing Science*, Vol.18, No.3, 333-351.
- Kotler, P. and Armstrong, G. (1996) *Principles of Marketing*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Kover, A.J., Goldberg, S.M., James, W.L. (1995) Creativity vs. effectiveness? An integrating classification for advertising. *Journal of Advertising Research*, Vol.35, No.6, 29-40.
- LaTour, M.S. and Zahra, S.A. (1989) Fear Appeals as Advertising Strategy: Should They Be Used?. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, Vol.6, No.3, 61-70.
- LaTour, M.S., Snipes, R.L., Bliss, S.J. (1996) Don't be afraid to use fear appeals: An experimental study. *Journal of Advertising Research*, Vol.36, No.2, 59-67
- Mattila, Anna S. (1999) Do emotional appeals work for services?. *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, Vol.10, No.3, 292-306.
- Mehta, A. and Purvis, S.C. (2006), "Reconsidering recall and emotion in advertising. *Journal of Advertising Research*, Vol.46, No.1, 49-56.
- Mizerski, Richard W. and J. Dennis White. (1986), "Understanding and Using Emotions in Advertising. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, Vol.3, No.Fall, 57-69.
- Naccarato, J. L. and Neuendorf, K. A. (1998) Content Analysis as a Predictive Methodology: Recall, Readership, and Evaluation of Business-to-Business Print Advertising. *Journal of Advertising Research*, No.May,19-33.
- Peracchio, Laura A., and Joan Meyers-Levy (1994), "How Ambiguous Cropped Objects in Ad Photos Can Affect Product Evaluations. *Journal of Consumer Research*, Vol. 21, No.1, 190-204.
- Pick, D.F., Sweeney, J. and Clay, J.A. (1991) Creative Advertising and the Von Restorff Effect. *Psychological Reports*, Vol.69, No.3, 923-926.
- Pieters, Rik G. M. and Klerk-Warmerdam, Marianne de (1996) Ad-Evoked and Recall Feelings Structure and Impact on Aad. *Journal of Business Research*, Vol.37, No.2, 105-114.
- Sasser, Sheila L. and Koslow, Scott. (2008) Desperately Seeking Advertising Creativity. *Journal of Advertising*, Vol.37, No.Winter, 5-19.

Schmitt, Carol L. and Blass, Thomas (2008), "Fear Appeals Revisited: Testing a Unique Anti-smoking Film. *Current Psychology*, Vol.27, No.2, 145-151

Smith, Robert E., Chen, Jiemiao and Yang, Xiaojing. (2008) The impact of advertising creativity on the hierarchy of effects. *Journal of Advertising*, Vol.37, No.4, 47-61.

Till, Brian D. and Baack, Daniel W. (2005), "RECALL AND PERSUASION Does Creative Advertising Matter?. *Journal of Advertising*, Vol.34 , No.Fall, 47-57.

Yang, X. and Smith, R.E. (2009) Beyond attention effects: Modeling the persuasive and emotional effects of advertising creativity. *Marketing Science*, Vol.28, No.5, 935-949.